

Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 11

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16759>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings magic squares of order 11 for **reduced entries**. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These **entries** are **non-sequential positive** and **negative numbers**. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe **decimal** or **fractional** values of entries depending on the types of magic squares. Different kind of magic squares are used to bring these **self-made** magic squares. These are of type, **block-wise**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered**, **double-digit bordered**, etc. In some cases, the idea of **magic rectangles** is also applied. In each case, the **magic rectangles** are considered with **equal width** and **length**. This work for the self-made algebraic magic squares order 11. This work is available online at above given link. For similar kind of work for different orders the readers are suggested to author's work given in references [30]-[45].*

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1 Introduction

This work brings **self-made algebraic** magic squares of order 11. By **self-made** or **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers of entries, where the magic square is complete in itself. Putting any integer values for these less entries, we shall get always a magic square. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more **sequential** numbers. These entries are **non-sequential positive** and/or **negative** numbers. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the way of choosing the entries. Sometime to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** entries we apply certain conditions. These conditions depends on the types of magic squares. The name **self-made** is not known in the literature of magic squares. It is being introduced for the first time. The work is based on different types of magic squares, such as, **pandiagonal, block-wise, cornered, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered**, etc. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** having equal width and length for the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality of width, still we have good results.

This work for the order 11 brings **magic, semi-magic** and **pandiagonal** magic squares. It is divided in three parts. The first part only on magic squares, the second part on **semi-magic** squares and the third part on **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 11. This is the only first part. For the second part refer the author’s work [43]. For more details on these kind of work refer author’s previous works [30]-[45]. The table below give the quantities and references for each order.

Order	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Total
3	1	1	0	2 [38]
4	2	0	2	4 [38]
5	2	1	3	6 [38]
6	5	1	6	12 [38]
7	5	3	8	16 [38]
8	8	5	13	26 [39]
9	10	9	18	28 [40]
10	15	14	29	58 [41]
11	25	23	to be done	48 [42, 43]
12	28	25	to be done	53 [44, 45]

The author [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] also worked similar kind of work but from different point of view. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of the magic squares.

2 Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are three different examples of magic squares of order 11 for sequential entries from 1 to 121.

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
	58	63	62	54	68	43	79	87	35	13	109	671
	65	61	57	55	67	78	44	25	97	104	18	671
	60	59	64	72	50	75	47	24	98	8	114	671
	56	52	53	73	71	38	84	89	33	3	119	671
	66	70	69	51	49	39	83	92	30	106	16	671
	81	37	40	76	77	74	42	29	93	5	117	671
	41	85	82	46	45	80	48	23	99	105	17	671
	21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671
	101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671
	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	
121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671	
119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	671	
117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	671	
115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	671	
11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	671	
13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	671	
15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	671	
17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	671	
19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671	
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671	
10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671	
100	22	85	79	42	55	44	50	72	94	28	671	
8	114	37	43	80	67	78	40	82	31	91	671	
107	15	49	73	62	63	58	76	46	24	98	671	
96	26	38	84	57	61	65	70	52	111	11	671	
35	87	66	56	64	59	60	69	53	25	97	671	
104	18	71	51	83	75	45	48	54	19	103	671	
6	116	81	41	39	47	77	74	68	120	2	671	
4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671	
89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

The first example is known by **cornered** magic squares. The second example is famous as **single-digit bordered** magic square. The third example is known as **double-digit bordered** magic square. For more details on these kind of magic squares refer author’s work [24, 25, 26, 27].

2.1 Self-Made Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are **twenty-five** results for **self-made** magic squares of order 11 for **reduced entries**.

Result 2.1. Let's consider following **self-made** magic square of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-T)/2-A41$	A43	$A57+A58+A59+A60+A61+A62-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A57$	$(R-T)/2-A58$	$(R-T)/2-A59$	$(R-T)/2-A60$	$(R-T)/2-A61$	$(R-T)/2-A62$	$2*R-A63-A42-9*(R-T)/2-A43$	$A41-R+9*(R-T)/4+A42+A63$
A42	A41	$7*(R-T)/4-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61-A62$	A57	A58	A59	A60	A61	A62	$R-A63-A41-A42-7*(R-T)/4$	A63
$A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	$T+A16+A30+A12-A24+A26-A20-A19-A23+A8-A22-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	$A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8+A22+A21-A16-A30-A12$	$7*(R-T)/4-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55$	$A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A35$	A35	A6	A7	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-A27-A31-A2-A10-A15$	$A24+A28+A27+A25+A20+A19+A29+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A2+A1-A34-3*A16-A32-A30-A12-A11-A10$	$T+A34+3*A16+A15+A32+A31+A30+A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A28-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A9-A6-A22-A5-A4-A1-A21$	A8	A9	A50	$(R-T)/2-A50$
$(R-T)/2-A36$	A36	$A24-A26-A25+A20+A23-A8-A6+A22+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A16-A14-2*A30-A12$	$A18-A16+A14+A33+A30-A13-A12-A11-2*A10+A25+A19+A23+A8-A7+A6-A22+A5-A34$	A10	A11	A12	A13	$T+A34-A18+2*A16-A33+A30+A12+A10-A24+A26-A20-A19-2*A23+A7-2*A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A51	$(R-T)/2-A51$
$(R-T)/2-A37$	A37	A14	$A34-A18-A17-2*A16-A15-A14-A30+A13-A12+2*A24-A26+A20+A19+A29+A23+A9-A8+A22+A21$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$T-A34+A16+A30-A13+A12-2*A24+A20-A19-A29-A23-A9+A8-A22-A21$	A52	$(R-T)/2-A52$
$(R-T)/2-A38$	A38	A19	A20	$T-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A21	A22	A23	A24	A53	$(R-T)/2-A53$
$(R-T)/2-A39$	A39	A25	A26	A27	$T+A34+2*A16+A30+A12+A10-A24-A28-A27-A25-A20-A19-A29-A23+A8+A7-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A28	$A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A34-2*A16-A30-A12-A10$	A29	A54	$(R-T)/2-A54$
$(R-T)/2-A40$	A40	A30	$T+A17+3*A16+A15-A33-A9+2*A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A6-A5-A1-A21$	A31	A32	$2*A24+A25+2*A20+2*A19+A29+2*A23+A9+A6+A5+A1+A21-A34-A17-3*A16-A15-A32-A31-A30-2*A12-A11-2*A10$	A33	A34	A55	$(R-T)/2-A55$
$A41+A63-A56$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A42+A63-A56$	$7*(R-T)/4-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49$	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A56	$A56-A41-(5*R-9*T)/2-A42-2*A63$
$A56+R-9*(R-T)/4-A42-A63$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A43-A42-A41-A63+A56$	$A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$(R-T)/2-A46$	$(R-T)/2-A47$	$(R-T)/2-A48$	$(R-T)/2-A49$	$A43+(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A42+A41+2*A63-A56$	$(R-T)/2-A56$

• **Details:**

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a magic square of order 7. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal width and length. The letters T and R represents the magic squares of orders 7 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.1. *Let's consider an example based on above result:*

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										162
	-20	52	336	-36	-37	-38	-39	-40	-41	-121	146	162
	51	50	-306	66	67	68	69	70	71	-116	72	162
	204	-174	-4	10	11	12	13	14	46	-264	294	162
	-14	44	15	16	53	24	-41	17	18	59	-29	162
	-15	45	-33	55	19	20	21	-2	22	60	-30	162
	-16	46	23	75	24	25	26	27	-98	61	-31	162
	-17	47	28	29	-81	30	31	32	33	62	-32	162
	-18	48	34	35	36	-50	37	-28	38	63	-33	162
	-19	49	39	-118	40	41	15	42	43	64	-34	162
	57	61	-228	53	54	55	56	57	58	65	-126	162
	-31	-106	258	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	229	-35	162
	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162

The magic square given in Example 2.1 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							102
	-4	10	11	12	13	14	46	102	
	15	16	53	24	-41	17	18	102	
	-33	55	19	20	21	-2	22	102	
	23	75	24	25	26	27	-98	102	
	28	29	-81	30	31	32	33	102	
	34	35	36	-50	37	-28	38	102	
	39	-118	40	41	15	42	43	102	
	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	

Result 2.2. Let's consider following **self-made** magic square of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-T)/2-A24$	A26	$A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A40$	$(R-T)/2-A41$	$(R-T)/2-A42$	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$2*R-A46-A25-9*(R-T)/2-A26$	$A24-R+9*(R-T)/4+A25+A46$
A25	A24	$7*(R-T)/4-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$R-A46-A24-A25-7*(R-T)/4$	A46
$A18+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	$(T-M)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	$7*(R-T)/4-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$	$A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A18$	A18	A13	A12	$3*(T-M)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A33	$(R-T)/2-A33$
$(R-T)/2-A19$	A19	$A15+A16-(T-M)/4$	$3*(T-M)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(T-M)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-M)/4$	A34	$(R-T)/2-A34$
$(R-T)/2-A20$	A20	$(T-M)/2-A15$	A15	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A7	$(T-M)/2-A7$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A21$	A21	$(T-M)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A22$	A22	A14-A6+A9	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-M)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*M-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A23$	A23	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A4$	$(T-M)/2-A5$	A14+A13-A6	$T-3*M-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$A24+A46-A39$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A25+A46-A39$	$7*(R-T)/4-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32$	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A39	$A39-A24-(5*R-9*T)/2-A25-2*A46$
$A39+R-9*(R-T)/4-A25-A46$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A26-A25-A24-A46+A39$	$A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A27$	$(R-T)/2-A28$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$A26+(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A25+A24+2*A46-A39$	$(R-T)/2-A39$

• **Details:**

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with another **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 having magic squares of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×3 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, T and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 7 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.2. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										152
	-7	35	244	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-54	87	152
	34	33	-218	49	50	51	52	53	54	-61	55	152
	112	-86	17	23	20	19	18	18	-15	-176	202	152
	-1	27	22	21	18	19	20	53	-53	42	-16	152
	-2	28	30	8	13	5	6	24	14	43	-17	152
	-3	29	14	24	1	8	15	16	22	44	-18	152
	-4	30	13	25	10	11	3	17	21	45	-19	152
	-5	31	26	60	30	13	14	-58	15	46	-20	152
	-6	32	-22	-61	8	25	24	30	96	47	-21	152
	40	32	-140	36	37	38	39	40	41	48	-59	152
	-6	-39	166	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	128	-22	152
	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152

The magic square given in Example 2.2 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						100					
	17	23	20	19	18	18	-15	100					
	22	21	18	19	20	53	-53	100	3	mgc	39	9	24
	30	8	13	5	6	24	14	100	18	13	5	6	24
	14	24	1	8	15	16	22	100	30	1	8	15	24
	13	25	10	11	3	17	21	100		10	11	3	24
	26	60	30	13	14	-58	15	100		24	24	24	24
	-22	-61	8	25	24	30	96	100					
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100					

Result 2.3. Let's consider following **self-made** magic square of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-T)/2-A24$	A26	$A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A40$	$(R-T)/2-A41$	$(R-T)/2-A42$	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$2*R-A46-A25-9*(R-T)/2-A26$	$A24-R+9*(R-T)/4+A25+A46$
A25	A24	$7*(R-T)/4-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$R-A46-A24-A25-7*(R-T)/4$	A46
$A18+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	A13	$T-S-A13$	$7*(R-T)/4-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$	$A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A18$	A18	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	A14	$T-S-A14$	A33	$(R-T)/2-A33$
$(R-T)/2-A19$	A19	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8$	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	A34	$(R-T)/2-A34$
$(R-T)/2-A20$	A20	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	A15	$T-S-A15$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A21$	A21	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	A16	$T-S-A16$	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A22$	A22	$T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13$	A10	$A7+A8+3*T/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13-3*S/2$	A11	A12	$(T-S)/2$	$3*S-2*T$	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A23$	A23	$A7-A10+A8-A14+A13$	$T-S-A10$	$S/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13-T/2$	$T-S-A11$	$T-S-A12$	$3*S-2*T$	$(T-S)/2$	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$A24+A46-A39$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A25+A46-A39$	$7*(R-T)/4-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32$	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A39	$A39-A24-(5*R-9*T)/2-A25-2*A46$
$A39+R-9*(R-T)/4-A25-A46$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A26-A25-A24-A46+A39$	$A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A27$	$(R-T)/2-A28$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$A26+(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A25+A24+2*A46-A39$	$(R-T)/2-A39$

• **Details:**

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 and 2×5 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T and R represents the magic sums of orders 5, 7 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.3. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										127
	-13	35	259	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-50	85	127
	34	33	-239	49	50	51	52	53	54	-65	55	127
	127	-107	10	11	1	12	13	22	18	-197	217	127
	-7	27	22	14	1	15	-5	23	17	42	-22	127
	-8	28	6	-1	16	24	2	6	34	43	-23	127
	-9	29	18	12	7	-10	20	24	16	44	-24	127
	-10	30	-9	11	22	6	17	25	15	45	-25	127
	-11	31	27	19	13	20	21	20	-33	46	-26	127
	-12	32	13	21	27	20	19	-33	20	47	-27	127
	40	24	-161	36	37	38	39	40	41	48	-55	127
	-4	-35	181	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	124	-28	127
	127	127	127	127	127	127	127	127	127	127	127	127

The magic square given in Example 2.3 includes the following magic squares:

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							87							
	10	11	1	12	13	22	18	87		pan	47	47	47	47	47	47
	22	14	1	15	-5	23	17	87	47	10	11	1	12	13	47	47
	6	-1	16	24	2	6	34	87	47	22	14	1	15	-5	47	47
	18	12	7	-10	20	24	16	87	47	6	-1	16	24	2	47	47
	-9	11	22	6	17	25	15	87	47	18	12	7	-10	20	47	47
	27	19	13	20	21	20	-33	87		-9	11	22	6	17	47	47
	13	21	27	20	19	-33	20	87	5	47	47	47	47	47	47	47
	87	87	87	87	87	87	87	87								

Result 2.4. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

$(R-T)/2-A22$	A24	$A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A38$	$(R-T)/2-A39$	$(R-T)/2-A40$	$(R-T)/2-A41$	$(R-T)/2-A42$	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$2*R-A44-A23-9*(R-T)/2-A24$	$A22-R+9*(R-T)/4+A23+A44$
A23	A22	$7*(R-T)/4-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	$R-A44-A22-A23-7*(R-T)/4$	A44
$A16+A17+A18+A19+A20+A21-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20-A21$	$R-T)/2-A22$	A24	$M8+M9+A40+A41+A42+A43-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-M8$	$(R-T)/2-M9$	$(R-T)/2-A40$	$(R-T)/2-A41$	$7*(R-T)/4-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36$	$A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A16$	A16	A23	A22	$7*(R-T)/4-M8-M9-A40-A41-A42-A43$	M8	M9	A40	A41	A31	$(R-T)/2-A31$
$(R-T)/2-A17$	A17	$A16+A17+A18+A19+A20+A21-5*(R-T)/2/2$	$7*(R-T)/2/2-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20-A21$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A32	$(R-T)/2-A32$
$(R-T)/2-A18$	A18	$(R-T)/2-A16$	A16	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A33	$(R-T)/2-A33$
$(R-T)/2-A19$	A19	$(R-T)/2-A17$	A17	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A34	$(R-T)/2-A34$
$(R-T)/2-A20$	A20	$(R-T)/2-A18$	A18	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A21$	A21	$(R-T)/2-A19$	A19	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$A22+A44-A37$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A23+A44-A37$	$7*(R-T)/4-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30$	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A30	A37	$A37-A22-(5*R-9*T)/2-A23-2*A44$
$A37+R-9*(R-T)/4-A23-A44$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A24-A23-A22-A44+A37$	$A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A25$	$(R-T)/2-A26$	$(R-T)/2-A27$	$(R-T)/2-A28$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$A24+(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A23+A22+2*A44-A37$	$(R-T)/2-A37$

• **Details:**

*It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7 having again a **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the upper-left corner containing the magic square of order 3. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 , 2×5 , and 2×3 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7 and 11 respectively. See below an example.*

Example 2.4. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										160
	-1	33	222	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-68	91	160
	32	31	-192	47	48	49	50	51	52	-61	53	160
	90	-60	15	1	2	16	14	20	32	-150	180	160
	5	25	-7	6	19	14	16	21	31	40	-10	160
	4	26	10	11	-3	15	15	22	30	41	-11	160
	3	27	20	13	12	15	-12	44	8	42	-12	160
	2	28	10	17	18	-12	15	23	29	43	-13	160
	1	29	70	17	18	6	19	26	-56	44	-14	160
	0	30	-18	35	34	46	33	-56	26	45	-15	160
	38	44	-114	34	35	36	37	38	39	46	-73	160
	-14	-53	144	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	138	-16	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

The magic square given in Example 2.4 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						100				
	15	1	2	16	14	20	32	100				
	-7	6	19	14	16	21	31	100				
	10	11	-3	15	15	22	30	100				
	20	13	12	15	-12	44	8	100				
	10	17	18	-12	15	23	29	100				
	70	17	18	6	19	26	-56	100				
	-18	35	34	46	33	-56	26	100				
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100				
	5	mgc	/ / / / /					48				
		15	1	2	16	14	48					
		-7	6	19	14	16	48					
		10	11	-3	15	15	48					
		20	13	12	15	-12	48					
		10	17	18	-12	15	48					
		48	48	48	48	48	48					
	3	mgc				18						
		15	1	2	18							
		-7	6	19	18							
		10	11	-3	18							
		18	18	18	18							

Result 2.5. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-T)/2-A25$	A27	$A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A41$	$(R-T)/2-A42$	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$(R-T)/2-A46$	$2*R-A47-A26-9*(R-T)/2-A27$	$A25-R+9*(R-T)/4+A26+A47$
A26	A25	$7*(R-T)/4-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46$	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	$R-A47-A25-A26-7*(R-T)/4$	A47
$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A6	$2*M-A9-S+A7$	$S-M-A7$	$S-M-A6$	A9	A14	T-S-A14	$7*(R-T)/4-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39$	$A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A19$	A19	$2*S-3*M+A9-2*A7+A2+A1-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$2*M-S+A4+2*A7-A2-A1-A9$	A15	T-S-A15	A34	$(R-T)/2-A34$
$(R-T)/2-A20$	A20	$2*A7+S-M-A6-A2-A1$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$A6-2*A7+A2+A1$	$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17-A16-A15-A14$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14+A15+A16+A17$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A21$	A21	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A22$	A22	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A9+2*S-3*M-A7$	A7	A6	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A23$	A23	$T-2*S-A7+A11+M+A6+A15-A14$	A11	$A7-(1/2)*S-M-A6+(3/2)*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$(R-T)/2-A24$	A24	$A7-A11+S-M-A6-A15+A14$	T-S-A11	$A13+A12+2*A11-A7+M+A6+A15-A14-(1/2)*T-(1/2)*S$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A39	$(R-T)/2-A39$
$A25+A47-A40$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A26+A47-A40$	$7*(R-T)/4-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A40	$A40-A25-(5*R-9*T)/2-A26-2*A47$
$A40+R-9*(R-T)/4-A26-A47$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A27-A26-A25-A47+A40$	$A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A28$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$(R-T)/2-A33$	$A27+(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A26+A25+2*A47-A40$	$(R-T)/2-A40$

• **Details:**

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7 having again a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 in the upper-left corner containing a magic square of order 3. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×5 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.5. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										160
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-77	100	160
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-70	56	160
	108	-78	15	-48	42	43	18	23	7	-168	198	160
	2	28	98	17	-3	-2	-40	24	6	43	-13	160
	1	29	54	-15	4	23	4	-23	53	44	-14	160
	0	30	13	10	11	-9	45	25	5	45	-15	160
	-1	31	-110	106	16	15	43	26	4	46	-16	160
	-2	32	-8	20	20	21	22	15	10	47	-17	160
	-3	33	38	10	10	9	8	10	15	48	-18	160
	41	47	-132	37	38	39	40	41	42	49	-82	160
	-17	-62	162	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	153	-19	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

The magic square given in Example 2.5 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							100						
	15	-48	42	43	18	23	7	100							
	98	17	-3	-2	-40	24	6	100							
	54	-15	4	23	4	-23	53	100							
	13	10	11	-9	45	25	5	100							
	-110	106	16	15	43	26	4	100							
	-8	20	20	21	22	15	10	100							
	38	10	10	9	8	10	15	100							
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100							

5	semi	/ / / / /					-80
	15	-48	42	43	18	70	
	98	17	-3	-2	-40	70	
	54	-15	4	23	4	70	
	13	10	11	-9	45	70	
	-110	106	16	15	43	70	
	70	70	70	70	70	70	

3	mgc				12
	17	-3	-2	12	
	-15	4	23	12	
	10	11	-9	12	
	12	12	12	12	

Result 2.6. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(T-S)/2-A28$	A29	$A20+A21+A22+A23-2*(T-S)$	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$(T-S)/2-A21$	$(T-S)/2-A22$	$(T-S)/2-A23$	$(7*S-3*T)/2-A14-A19-A29$	$A28+2*T-3*S+A14+A19$	$5*S+A17-A8+A18+A32-A7+A39$	$R-T-5*S-A17+A8-A18-A32+A7-A39$
A30	A28	$5*(T-S)/2-A20-A21-A22-A23$	A20	A21	A22	A23	$(5*S-3*T)/2-A28-A14-A19$	$A14+A19-A30$	A39	$R-T-A39$
$A24+A25+A26+A27-2*(T-S)$	$5*(T-S)/2-A24-A25-A26-A27$	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	$5*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18-2*(T-S)$	$9*(R-T)/2-A40-A43-A42-A41-A44-A45-2*A39-5*S-A17+A8-A18-A32+A7$	$7*(T-R)/2+2*A39+5*S+A17-A8+A18+A32-A7+A40+A43+A42+A41+A44+A45$
$(T-S)/2-A24$	A24	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	A15	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A40	$R-T-A40$
$(T-S)/2-A25$	A25	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8$	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	A16	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A41	$R-T-A41$
$(T-S)/2-A26$	A26	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	A17	$(T-S)/2-A17$	A42	$R-T-A42$
$(T-S)/2-A27$	A27	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	A18	$(T-S)/2-A18$	A43	$R-T-A43$
$(7*S-3*T)/2-A14-A30-A29$	$(5*S-3*T)/2-A14-A28-A29$	$5*(T-S)/2-A10-A11-A12-A13$	A10	A11	A12	A13	$(3*T-7*S)/2+A28+2*A14+A19+A29$	$A29-A19+A30$	A44	$R-T-A44$
$2*T-3*S+A28+A14+A29$	A14	$A10+A11+A12+A13-2*(T-S)$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	$(T-S)/2-A12$	$(T-S)/2-A13$	A19	$3*S-T-A28-2*A14-A19-A29$	A45	$R-T-A45$
$R-6*T+A11+2*A10+A16+2*A15+A13+A12$	A32	$(7*R+3*T)/2-A38-A37-A35-A32-A36-A34-A33-A11-2*A10-A16-2*A15-A13-A12$	A33	A34	A35	a36	A37	A38	$(R-T)/2$	$5*T-4*R$
$5*T-A11-2*A10-A16-2*A15-A13-A12$	$R-T-A32$	$A38+A37+A35+A32+A36+A34+A33+A11+2*A10+A16+2*A15+A13+A12-5*(T+R)/2$	$R-T-A33$	$R-T-A34$	$R-T-A35$	$R-T-A36$	$R-T-A37$	$R-T-A38$	$5*T-4*R$	$(R-T)/2$

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 having **adouble-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. It contains **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×9 and 2×5 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 5, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.6. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										200
	-3	39	-14	5	4	3	2	3	131	611	-581	200
	40	38	49	30	31	32	33	-96	13	49	-19	200
	2	33	11	12	50	13	14	69	-34	-840	870	200
	1	34	23	15	2	16	44	25	10	50	-20	200
	0	35	7	48	17	25	3	26	9	51	-21	200
	-1	36	19	13	8	39	21	27	8	52	-22	200
	-2	37	40	12	23	7	18	28	7	53	-23	200
	-8	-106	89	20	21	22	23	59	50	54	-24	200
	141	24	-54	15	14	13	12	29	-24	55	-25	200
	-638	42	458	43	44	45	46	47	48	15	50	200
	668	-12	-428	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	50	15	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

The magic square given in Example 2.6 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									170
	-3	39	-14	5	4	3	2	3	131		170
	40	38	49	30	31	32	33	-96	13		170
	2	33	11	12	50	13	14	69	-34		170
	1	34	23	15	2	16	44	25	10		170
	0	35	7	48	17	25	3	26	9		170
	-1	36	19	13	8	39	21	27	8		170
	-2	37	40	12	23	7	18	28	7		170
	-8	-106	89	20	21	22	23	59	50		170
	141	24	-54	15	14	13	12	29	-24		170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		170

	pan	100	100	100	100	100
100	11	12	50	13	14	100
100	23	15	2	16	44	100
100	7	48	17	25	3	100
100	19	13	8	39	21	100
	40	12	23	7	18	100
5	100	100	100	100	100	100

Result 2.7. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(S-L)/2+A28+2*A12+A17-A18$	A28	$3*(S-L)/4+A19+A20+A21+A22$	$(L-S)/2-A19$	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(5*S-L)/4-A28-A12-A17$	$(L-S)/2-A28-A12+A18$	A37	R-L-A37
$(9*S-5*L)/4+A17-A23+A12$	$L-S-A28-2*A12-A17+A18$	$5*(L-S)/4-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A19	A20	A21	A22	A28+A12-A18	A23	A38	R-L-A38
$3*(S-L)/4+A24+A25+A26+A27$	$5*(L-S)/4-A24-A25-A26-A27$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$5*(L-S)/4-A13-A14-A15-A16$	$3*(S-L)/4+A13+A14+A15+A16$	A39	R-L-A39
$(L-S)/2-A24$	A24	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A13	$(L-S)/2-A13$	A40	R-L-A40
$(L-S)/2-A25$	A25	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A14	$(L-S)/2-A14$	A41	R-L-A41
$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	A15	$(L-S)/2-A15$	A42	R-L-A42
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	$A1+3*(S-M)/2-A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$	A43	R-L-A43
$L-S-A28-2*A12+A18-2*A17+A23$	A12	$5*(L-S)/4-A8-A9-A10-A11$	A8	A9	A10	A11	A17	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A28+A12-A18+A17-A23$	A44	R-L-A44
$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A12+A17-A18$	$3*(S-L)/4+A8+A9+A10+A11$	$(L-S)/2-A8$	$(L-S)/2-A9$	$(L-S)/2-A10$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	A18	$(L-S)/2-A17$	$(9/2)*R-(9/2)*L-A39-A38-A37-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A39+A38+A37+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40$
$R-(7/2)*L+2*A8+A10+A30+2*A4+2*A13+A14+A11+A16+2*A5+A15+A9+A38-A37+2*S-A1-A2-(1/2)*M$	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	$(7/2)*R-2*A8-A35-A34-A10-2*A30-2*A4-2*A13-A14-A33-A11-A16-A32-2*A5-A31-A15-A9-A38+A37-A36-2*S+A1+A2+(1/2)*M-L$	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
$(5/2)*L-2*A8-A10-A30-2*A4-2*A13-A14-A11-A16-2*A5-A15-A9-A38+A37-2*S+A1+A2+(1/2)*M$	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$2*A8+A35+A34+A10+2*A30+2*A4+2*A13+A14+A33+A11+A16+A32+2*A5+A31+A15+A9+A38-A37+A36+2*S-A1-A2-(1/2)*M-(5/2)*R$	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 having a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. It again contains a **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×9 and 2×5 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.7. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										140
	142	91	226	-32	-35	-38	-41	-172	-41	118	-78	140
	-19	-110	-194	64	67	70	73	73	76	121	-81	140
	286	-254	17	-1	2	-20	38	-122	154	124	-84	140
	-47	79	-9	6	21	22	-4	46	-14	127	-87	140
	-50	82	10	13	-5	25	-7	49	-17	130	-90	140
	-53	85	56	19	-48	9	0	52	-20	133	-93	140
	-56	88	-38	-1	66	0	9	55	-23	136	-96	140
	-92	43	-62	31	34	37	40	58	11	139	-99	140
	-11	-4	94	1	-2	-5	-8	61	-26	-848	888	140
	433	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	-995	20	-60	140
	-393	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	-75	1035	-60	20	140
	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140

The magic square given in Example 2.7 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									100
	142	91	226	-32	-35	-38	-41	-172	-41		100
	-19	-110	-194	64	67	70	73	73	76		100
	286	-254	17	-1	2	-20	38	-122	154		100
	-47	79	-9	6	21	22	-4	46	-14		100
	-50	82	10	13	-5	25	-7	49	-17		100
	-53	85	56	19	-48	9	0	52	-20		100
	-56	88	-38	-1	66	0	9	55	-23		100
	-92	43	-62	31	34	37	40	58	11		100
	-11	-4	94	1	-2	-5	-8	61	-26		100
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		100

5	mgc	/ / / / /					36
	17	-1	2	-20	38	36	
	-9	6	21	22	-4	36	
	10	13	-5	25	-7	36	
	56	19	-48	9	0	36	
	-38	-1	66	0	9	36	
	36	36	36	36	36	36	

3	mgc	/ / /			18
	17	-1	2		18
	-9	6	21		18
	10	13	-5		18
	18	18	18		18

Result 2.8. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(S-L)/2+A31+2*A15+A20-A21$	A31	$3*(S-L)/4+A22+A23+A24+A25$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(L-S)/2-A25$	$(5*S-L)/4-A31-A15-A20$	$(L-S)/2-A31-A15+A21$	A40	R-L-A40
$(9*S-5*L)/4+A20-A26+A15$	$L-S-A31-2*A15-A20+A21$	$5*(L-S)/4-A22-A23-A24-A25$	A22	A23	A24	A25	$A31+A15-A21$	A26	A41	R-L-A41
$3*(S-L)/4+A27+A28+A29+A30$	$5*(L-S)/4-A27-A28-A29-A30$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	S-M-A7	A8	A9	$5*(L-S)/4-A16-A17-A18-A19$	$3*(S-L)/4+A16+A17+A18+A19$	A42	R-L-A42
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$	A43	R-L-A43
$(L-S)/2-A28$	A28	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	S-M-A5	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$	A44	R-L-A44
$(L-S)/2-A29$	A29	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$	A45	R-L-A45
$(L-S)/2-A30$	A30	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	A19	$(L-S)/2-A19$	A46	R-L-A46
$L-S-A31-2*A15+A21-2*A20+A26$	A15	$5*(L-S)/4-A11-A12-A13-A14$	A11	A12	A13	A14	A20	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A31+A15-A21+A20-A26$	A47	R-L-A47
$(L-S)/2-A15$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A15+A20-A21$	$3*(S-L)/4+A11+A12+A13+A14$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(L-S)/2-A13$	$(L-S)/2-A14$	A21	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$(9/2)*R-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-(9/2)*L$	$A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40+(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R$
$R+A7+A12+A13+A14+A33+2*A11+A17+A18+A19+2*A16-A5-A1+(5/2)*S-A2+A41-(7/2)*L-A40$	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	$(7/2)*R-A35-A34-A7-A12-A13-A14-2*A33-2*A11-A17-A18-A19-2*A16+A5-A39-A38-A37-A36-(5/2)*S+A1+A2-A41-L+A40$	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
$(5/2)*L-A7-A12-A13-A14-A33-2*A11-A17-A18-A19-2*A16+A5+A1-(5/2)*S+A2-A41+A40$	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	$A35+A34+A7+A12+A13+A14+2*A33+2*A11+A17+A18+A19+2*A16-A5+A39+A38+A37+A36+(5/2)*S-A1-A2+A41-A40-(5/2)*R$	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 having a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper-left corner. It again contains a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 with magic square of order 3 in the inner part. The magic rectangles of orders 2×9 and 2×5 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.8. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										180	
		39	40	58	17	16	15	14	-89	14	49	7	180
		-74	9	-10	31	32	33	34	34	35	50	6	180
		78	-30	15	-16	-6	17	18	14	34	51	5	180
		12	36	-12	15	1	2	22	25	23	52	4	180
		11	37	14	-7	6	19	-4	26	22	53	3	180
		10	38	13	10	11	-3	-3	27	21	54	2	180
		9	39	-2	26	16	-7	-5	28	20	55	1	180
		15	24	34	20	21	22	23	29	-64	56	0	180
		24	-69	14	28	27	26	25	30	19	-168	224	180
		77	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	-140	28	-100	180
		-21	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	196	-100	28	180
		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

The magic square given in Example 2.8 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi											130
		39	40	58	17	16	15	14	-89	14	124	
		-74	9	-10	31	32	33	34	34	35	124	
		78	-30	15	-16	-6	17	18	14	34	124	
		12	36	-12	15	1	2	22	25	23	124	
		11	37	14	-7	6	19	-4	26	22	124	
		10	38	13	10	11	-3	-3	27	21	124	
		9	39	-2	26	16	-7	-5	28	20	124	
		15	24	34	20	21	22	23	29	-64	124	
		24	-69	14	28	27	26	25	30	19	124	
		124	124	124	124	124	124	124	124	124	124	

5	semi						34
		15	-16	-6	17	18	28
		-12	15	1	2	22	28
		14	-7	6	19	-4	28
		13	10	11	-3	-3	28
		-2	26	16	-7	-5	28
		28	28	28	28	28	28

3	mgc				18
		15	1	2	18
		-7	6	19	18
		10	11	-3	18
		18	18	18	18

Result 2.9. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A23	L-T-A23	A37	R-L-A37
A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A24	L-T-A24	A38	R-L-A38
$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A25	L-T-A25	A39	R-L-A39
$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	S/3	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A26	L-T-A26	A40	R-L-A40
$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	S-A1-A2	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$	$9*(R-L)/2-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44$	$7*(L-R)/2+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44$
$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A27	L-T-A27	A41	R-L-A41
$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A28	L-T-A28	A42	R-L-A42
A18	$(5*T-3*S)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*S)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*S-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$5*T-(7*L+3*S)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$	A44	R-L-A44
A30	$3*(T-S)/2-R+A25-A26+A30+2*A14+2*A9-A12+A13-A6+A8+A5-A20+A19+A37-A38$	A31	A32	$(3*S-3*T-9*L+11*R)/2-A25+A26-2*A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-2*A14-2*A9+A12-A13+A6-A8-A5+A20-A19-A37+A38$	A33	A34	A35	A36	$(R-L)/2$	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A30	$2*R-L-3*(T-S)/2-A37+A38-A25+A26-A30-2*A14-2*A9+A12-A13+A6-A8-A5+A20-A19$	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	$(3*T-9*R+7*L-3*S)/2+A25-A26+2*A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+2*A14+2*A9-A12+A13-A6+A8+A5-A20+A19+A37-A38$	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$5*L-4*R$	$(R-L)/2$

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 having a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. It contains the magic squares of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.9. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										180
	-2	24	31	0	-1	19	29	33	-13	47	13	180
	23	22	-11	20	21	-9	34	34	-14	48	12	180
	41	-21	3	28	29	-5	25	35	-15	49	11	180
	-5	25	46	20	-6	17	3	36	-16	50	10	180
	-6	26	11	12	37	18	2	-143	163	-134	194	180
	27	-2	1	14	15	29	16	37	-17	51	9	180
	22	26	19	6	5	31	-9	38	-18	52	8	180
	28	-5	29	30	-75	31	32	10	40	53	7	180
	-8	25	-9	-10	95	-11	-12	40	10	54	6	180
	40	21	41	42	-52	43	44	45	46	30	-120	180
	20	39	19	18	112	17	16	15	14	-120	30	180
	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

The magic square given in Example 2.9 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

12	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									120
	-2	24	31	0	-1	19	29	33	-13	120	
	23	22	-11	20	21	-9	34	34	-14	120	
	41	-21	3	28	29	-5	25	35	-15	120	
	-5	25	46	20	-6	17	3	36	-16	120	
	-6	26	11	12	37	18	2	-143	163	120	
	27	-2	1	14	15	29	16	37	-17	120	
	22	26	19	6	5	31	-9	38	-18	120	
	28	-5	29	30	-75	31	32	10	40	120	
	-8	25	-9	-10	95	-11	-12	40	10	120	
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	

7	mgc							100
	-2	24	31	0	-1	19	29	100
	23	22	-11	20	21	-9	34	100
	41	-21	3	28	29	-5	25	100
	-5	25	46	20	-6	17	3	100
	-6	26	11	12	37	18	2	100
	27	-2	1	14	15	29	16	100
	22	26	19	6	5	31	-9	100
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

3	mgc	9	111	60
87	3	28	29	60
33	46	20	-6	60
	11	12	37	60
	60	60	60	60

Result 2.10. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	$2*L-5*T-A23-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	$4*T-L+A23+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	A37	R-L-A37
A8-A2+A7	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	L-T-A23	A23	$A37-R-4*T+A29-A30+7*L/2+A25-A24+5*S/2-A21-A20-2*A19-A22+A16+2*A15+2*A12-2*A18$	$2*R-9*L/2-A37+4*T-A29+A30-A25+A24-5*S/2+A21+A20+2*A19+A22-A16-2*A15-2*A12+2*A18$
$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	L-T-A24	A24	$4*T+11*R/2-A38-A29-A41-A40+A30-A39-A42-A43-8*L-A25+A24-5*S/2+A21+A20+2*A19+A22-A16-2*A15-2*A12+2*A18-2*A37$	$2*A37-4*T-9*R/2+A38+A29+A41+A40-A30+A39+A42+A43+7*L+A25-A24+5*S/2-A21-A20-2*A19-A22+A16+2*A15+2*A12-2*A18$
A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A25	A25	A38	R-L-A38
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	$(13*T-7*L)/2+A25+A24+2*A23+A27+A26+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	$(9*L-15*T)/2-A25-A24-2*A23-A27-A26-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	A39	R-L-A39
T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	$A7+A8+3*(T-S)/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	L-T-A26	A26	A40	R-L-A40
A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	$(S-T)/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A27	A27	A41	R-L-A41
A18	$A18-2*A15-A12$	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A20-A19-A22+2*A15+A12-2*A18$	A19	A20	A21	A22	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A18	$L-T+2*A15+A12-A18$	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A20+A19+A22-2*A15-A12+2*A18$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	A43	R-L-A43
A29	A30	$9*(R-L)/2-A36-A35-A33-A30-A34-A32-A31-A29$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A29	R-L-A30	$7*(L-R)/2+A36+A35+A33+A30+A34+A32+A31+A29$	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11, 9 and 7 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.10. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										220
	21	22	-10	23	24	33	7	56	-6	57	-7	220
	33	25	12	26	-16	34	6	7	43	45	5	220
	17	-12	27	35	13	-38	78	6	44	-240	290	220
	29	23	18	-21	31	35	5	5	45	58	-8	220
	-20	22	33	17	28	36	4	94	-44	59	-9	220
	16	30	-9	31	32	20	0	4	46	60	-10	220
	24	10	49	9	8	0	20	3	47	61	-11	220
	38	-64	39	39	40	41	42	25	-30	62	-12	220
	12	114	11	11	10	9	8	-30	25	63	-13	220
	49	50	-195	51	52	53	54	55	56	25	-30	220
	1	0	245	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-30	25	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The magic square given in Example 2.10 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									170
	21	22	-10	23	24	33	7	56	-6	170	
	33	25	12	26	-16	34	6	7	43	170	
	17	-12	27	35	13	-38	78	6	44	170	
	29	23	18	-21	31	35	5	5	45	170	
	-20	22	33	17	28	36	4	94	-44	170	
	16	30	-9	31	32	20	0	4	46	170	
	24	10	49	9	8	0	20	3	47	170	
	38	-64	39	39	40	41	42	25	-30	170	
	12	114	11	11	10	9	8	-30	25	170	
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	

7	mgc							120
	21	22	-10	23	24	33	7	120
	33	25	12	26	-16	34	6	120
	17	-12	27	35	13	-38	78	120
	29	23	18	-21	31	35	5	120
	-20	22	33	17	28	36	4	120
	16	30	-9	31	32	20	0	120
	24	10	49	9	8	0	20	120
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

5	pan	80	80	80	80	80
80	21	22	-10	23	24	80
80	33	25	12	26	-16	80
80	17	-12	27	35	13	80
80	29	23	18	-21	31	80
	-20	22	33	17	28	80
	80	80	80	80	80	80

Result 2.11. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A21	L-T-A21	A35	R-L-A35
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A22	L-T-A22	A36	R-L-A36
A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A23	L-T-A23	$9*(R-L)/2-A37-A40-A39-A38-A41-A42-A36-A35$	$7*(L-R)/2+A36+A35+A37+A40+A39+A38+A41+A42$
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$	A24	L-T-A24	A37	R-L-A37
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$	A38	R-L-A38
$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A25	L-T-A25	A39	R-L-A39
$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A26	L-T-A26	A40	R-L-A40
A16	$5*S-4*T-L+A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A12+A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14$	A17	A18	$(9*L+T)/2-5*S-2*A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14-A17-A18-A19-A20$	A19	A20	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A16	$2*L+3*T-5*S-A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14$	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	$5*S-(3*T+7*L)/2+2*A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A12+A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14+A17+A18+A19+A20$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	A42	R-L-A42
A28	$(5*S-T)/2+A28+A17-A18+A10+A14-A24+A23-A36+A35-R$	$(11*R-9*L+T-5*S)/2-A34-A33-A31-2*A28-A17+A18-A10-A14+A24-A23+A36-A35-A32-A30-A29$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A28	$2*R-L-A28+(T-5*S)/2-A17+A18-A10-A14+A24-A23+A36-A35$	$(7*L-9*R+5*S-T)/2+A34+A33+A31+2*A28+A17-A18+A10+A14-A24+A23-A36+A35+A32+A30+A29$	R-L-A29	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11, 9, 7 and 5 having a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.11. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										250
	13	8	9	74	-4	21	29	31	19	45	5	250
	6	10	14	15	55	22	28	32	18	46	4	250
	11	12	7	16	54	23	27	33	17	-163	213	250
	2	14	89	35	-40	35	15	34	16	47	3	250
	68	56	-19	-40	35	24	26	-26	76	48	2	250
	39	18	19	29	20	25	0	35	15	49	1	250
	11	32	31	21	30	0	25	36	14	50	0	250
	26	-32	27	28	67	29	30	25	0	51	-1	250
	24	82	23	22	-17	21	20	0	25	52	-2	250
	38	4	-66	39	40	41	42	43	44	25	0	250
	12	46	116	11	10	9	8	7	6	0	25	250
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

The magic square given in Example 2.11 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										200
	13	8	9	74	-4	21	29	31	19			200
	6	10	14	15	55	22	28	32	18			200
	11	12	7	16	54	23	27	33	17			200
	2	14	89	35	-40	35	15	34	16			200
	68	56	-19	-40	35	24	26	-26	76			200
	39	18	19	29	20	25	0	35	15			200
	11	32	31	21	30	0	25	36	14			200
	26	-32	27	28	67	29	30	25	0			200
	24	82	23	22	-17	21	20	0	25			200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

7	mgc									150
	13	8	9	74	-4	21	29			150
	6	10	14	15	55	22	28			150
	11	12	7	16	54	23	27			150
	2	14	89	35	-40	35	15			150
	68	56	-19	-40	35	24	26			150
	39	18	19	29	20	25	0			150
	11	32	31	21	30	0	25			150
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150			150

5	mgc						100
	13	8	9	74	-4	100	
	6	10	14	15	55	100	
	11	12	7	16	54	100	
	2	14	89	35	-40	100	
	68	56	-19	-40	35	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	

3	mgc				30
	13	8	9	30	
	6	10	14	30	
	11	12	7	30	
	30	30	30	30	

Result 2.12. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

A6	$2*M-A9-S+A7$	$S-M-A7$	$S-M-A6$	A9	A14	T-S-A14	$2*L-5*T-A24-A7+2*S+2*A15+2*A11+2*A12+A17$	$4*T-L+A24+A7-2*S-2*A15-2*A11-2*A12-A17$	A37	R-L-A37
$2*S-3*M+A9-2*A7+A2+A1-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$2*M-S+A4+2*A7-A2-A1-A9$	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A24	A24	A38	R-L-A38
$2*A7+S-M-A6-A2-A1$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$A6-2*A7+A2+A1$	$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17-A16-A15-A14$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14+A15+A16+A17$	L-T-A25	A25	A39	R-L-A39
A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	L-T-A26	A26	A40	R-L-A40
$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A9+2*S-3*M-A7$	A7	A6	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	$(13*T-7*L)/2+A26+A25+2*A24+A28+A27+A7-2*S-2*A15-2*A11-2*A12-A17$	$(9*L-15*T)/2-A26-A25-2*A24-A28-A27-A7+2*S+2*A15+2*A11+2*A12+A17$	A41	R-L-A41
$T-2*S-A7+A11+M+A6+A15-A14$	A11	$A7-(1/2)*S-M-A6+(3/2)*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	L-T-A27	A27	A42	R-L-A42
$A7-A11+S-M-A6-A15+A14$	T-S-A11	$A13+A12+2*A11-A7+M+A6+A15-A14-(1/2)*T-(1/2)*S$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A28	A28	A43	R-L-A43
A19	$A19-2*A16-A13$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*T-A22-A21-A20-A23+2*A16+A13-2*A19$	A20	A21	A22	A23	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A19	$L-T+2*A16+A13-A19$	$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*L+A22+A21+A20+A23-2*A16-A13+2*A19$	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	$(9/2)*R-(9/2)*L-A39-A38-A37-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A39+A38+A37+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40$
$R+4*T-A26+A25+A23+A21+A22+A30+2*A20-2*A13-A17+2*A19-2*A16+A38-A37-(5/2)*S-(7/2)*L$	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	$(7/2)*R-4*T-A35-A34+A26-A25-A23-A21-A22-2*A30-2*A20+2*A13-A33+A17-2*A19+2*A16-A32-A31-A38+A37-A36+(5/2)*S-L$	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
$(5/2)*L-4*T+A26-A25-A23-A21-A22-A30-2*A20+2*A13+A17-2*A19+2*A16-A38+A37+(5/2)*S$	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$4*T+A35+A34-A26+A25+A23+A21+A22+2*A30+2*A20-2*A13+A33-A17+2*A19-2*A16+A32+A31+A38-A37+A36-(5/2)*S-(5/2)*R$	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11, 9 and 7 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. It contains magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.12. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										250
	16	58	13	14	19	24	6	2	48	47	3	250
	-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	16	34	48	2	250
	25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	15	35	49	1	250
	14	11	12	67	16	26	4	14	36	50	0	250
	101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	103	-53	51	-1	250
	21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	13	37	52	-2	250
	9	9	42	8	7	60	15	12	38	53	-3	250
	29	-46	66	30	31	32	33	25	0	54	-4	250
	21	96	-16	20	19	18	17	0	25	-179	229	250
	-21	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	-55	25	0	250
	71	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	105	0	25	250
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

The magic square given in Example 2.12 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									200
	16	58	13	14	19	24	6	2	48	200	
	-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	16	34	200	
	25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	15	35	200	
	14	11	12	67	16	26	4	14	36	200	
	101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	103	-53	200	
	21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	13	37	200	
	9	9	42	8	7	60	15	12	38	200	
	29	-46	66	30	31	32	33	25	0	200	
	21	96	-16	20	19	18	17	0	25	200	
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	

7	mgc								150
	16	58	13	14	19	24	6	150	
	-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	150	
	25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	150	
	14	11	12	67	16	26	4	150	
	101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	150	
	21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	150	
	9	9	42	8	7	60	15	150	
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	

5	semi						210
	16	58	13	14	19	120	
	-36	-7	48	49	66	120	
	25	86	30	-26	5	120	
	14	11	12	67	16	120	
	101	-28	17	16	14	120	
	120	120	120	120	120	120	

3	mgc				90
	-7	48	49	90	
	86	30	-26	90	
	11	12	67	90	
	90	90	90	90	

Result 2.13. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with reduced entries:*

$T+A16+A30+A12-A24+A26-A20-A19-A23+A8-A22-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	$A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8+A22+A21-A16-A30-A12$	A41	L-T-A41	A55	R-L-A55
A6	A7	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-A27-A31-A2-A10-A15$	$A24+A28+A27+A25+A20+A19+A29+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A2+A1-A34-3*A16-A32-A30-A12-A11-A10$	$T+A34+3*A16+A15+A32+A31+A30+A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A28-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A9-A6-A22-A5-A4-A1-A21$	A8	A9	A42	L-T-A42	A56	R-L-A56
$A24-A26-A25+A20+A23-A8-A6+A22+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A16-A14-2*A30-A12$	$A18-A16+A14+A33+A30-A13-A12-A11-2*A10+A25+A19+A23+A8-A7+A6-A22+A5-A34$	A10	A11	A12	$T+A34-A18+2*A16-A33+A30+A12+A10-A24+A26-A20-A19-2*A23+A7-2*A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A13	A43	L-T-A43	A57	R-L-A57
A14	$A34-A18-A17-2*A16-A15-A14-A30+A13-A12+2*A24-A26+A20+A19+A29+A23+A9-A8+A22+A21$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$T-A34+A16+A30-A13+A12-2*A24+A26-A20-A19-A29-A23-A9+A8-A22-A21$	A44	L-T-A44	A58	R-L-A58
A19	A20	$T-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A21	A22	A23	A24	A45	L-T-A45	A59	R-L-A59
A25	A26	A27	$T+A34+2*A16+A30+A12+A10-A24-A28-A27-A25-A20-A19-A29-A23+A8+A7-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A28	$A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A34-2*A16-A30-A12-A10$	A29	A46	L-T-A46	A60	R-L-A60
A30	$T+A17+3*A16+A15-A33-A9+2*A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A6-A5-A1-A21$	A31	A32	$2*A24+A25+2*A20+2*A19+A29+2*A23+A9+A6+A5+A1+A21-A34-A17-3*A16-A15-A32-A31-A30-2*A12-A11-2*A10$	A33	A34	$7*(L-T)/2-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46$	$5*(T-L)/2+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46$	A61	R-L-A61
$A36-A1-A21+A31-A5-A4-A3-A2-A29-A23+A8+A7-A25-A20-A19-A10-A24-A28-A27+2*A16+A30+A12+A22+A34+A13+A18-A41+A42+L-T$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$A1+A21-A31+A5+A4+A3+A2+A29+A23-A8-A7+A25+A20+A19-A10+A24+A28+A27-2*A16-A30-A12-A22-A34-A13-A18+A41-A42+(5/2)*L-(5/2)*T-A40-A39-A38-A37-2*A36$	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A62	R-L-A62
$A1+A21-A31+A5+A4+A3+A2+A29+A23-A8-A7+A25+A20+A19-A10+A24+A28+A27-2*A16-A30-A12-A22-A34-A13-A18+A41-A42-A36$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$(3/2)*T+A40+A39+A38+A37+2*A36-A1-A21+A31-A5-A4-A3-A2-A29-A23+A8+A7-A25-A20-A19-A10-A24-A28-A27+2*A16+A30+A12+A22+A34+A13+A18-A41+A42-(3/2)*L$	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	$(9/2)*R-(9/2)*L-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61-A62$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59+A60+A61+A62$
$R-2*T-A8-2*A34-A26+A25+3*A23+2*A21-A7+4*A24-3*A10-2*A30+A6+A29+3*A20+A4-3*A12-A11-A17+3*A19-5*A16-A32+2*A5-A31-A15+A9-A55+A56+A38-A37+A3+2*A1+A2+A48+A44-A43$	A48	A49	A50	A51	A52	A53	A54	$(7/2)*R+2*T+A8+2*A34+A26-A50-A25-3*A23-A49-2*A21+A7-A54-4*A24+3*A10+2*A30-A6-A29-A53-3*A20-A4+3*A12+A11+A17-3*A19+5*A16+A32-2*A5+A31-A51-A52+A15-A9+A55-A56-A38+A37-A3-2*A1-A2-2*A48-A44+A43-(9/2)*L$	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
$2*T+A8+2*A34+A26-A25-3*A23-2*A21+A7-4*A24+3*A10+2*A30-A6-A29-3*A20-A4+3*A12+A11+A17-3*A19+5*A16+A32-2*A5+A31+A15-A9+A55-A56-A38+A37-A3-2*A1-A2-A48-A44+A43-L$	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	$A50+A25+3*A23+A49+2*A21-A7+A54+4*A24-3*A10-2*A30+A6+A29+A53+3*A20+A4-3*A12-A11-A17+3*A19-5*A16-A32+2*A5-A31+A51+A52-A15+A9-A55+A56+A38-A37+A3+2*A1+A2+2*A48+A44-A43+(7/2)*L-(5/2)*R-2*T-A8-2*A34-A26$	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 having a magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.13. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										161
	-13	11	12	13	14	15	47	51	-29	65	-25	161
	16	17	54	25	-50	18	19	52	-30	66	-26	161
	-32	56	20	21	22	-11	23	53	-31	67	-27	161
	24	76	25	26	27	28	-107	54	-32	68	-28	161
	29	30	-90	31	32	33	34	55	-33	69	-29	161
	35	36	37	-59	38	-27	39	56	-34	70	-30	161
	40	-127	41	42	16	43	44	-244	266	71	-31	161
	35	46	47	48	49	50	-198	11	33	72	-32	161
	-13	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	220	33	11	-368	408	161
	47	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	-294	20	-39	161
	-7	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	334	-39	20	161
	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161

The magic square given in Example 2.13 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									121
	-13	11	12	13	14	15	47	51	-29	121	
	16	17	54	25	-50	18	19	52	-30	121	
	-32	56	20	21	22	-11	23	53	-31	121	
	24	76	25	26	27	28	-107	54	-32	121	
	29	30	-90	31	32	33	34	55	-33	121	
	35	36	37	-59	38	-27	39	56	-34	121	
	40	-127	41	42	16	43	44	-244	266	121	
	35	46	47	48	49	50	-198	11	33	121	
	-13	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	220	33	11	121	
	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	

2	mgc								99
	-13	11	12	13	14	15	47	99	
	16	17	54	25	-50	18	19	99	
	-32	56	20	21	22	-11	23	99	
	24	76	25	26	27	28	-107	99	
	29	30	-90	31	32	33	34	99	
	35	36	37	-59	38	-27	39	99	
	40	-127	41	42	16	43	44	99	
	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	

Result 2.14. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18	L-T-A25	A25	A39	R-L-A39
A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14	L-T-A26	A26	A40	R-L-A40
5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17	5*(T-L)/2+K2+A25+A27+A28+A29+A30	7*(L-T)/2-A26-A25-A27-A28-A29-A30	A41	R-L-A41
A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15	L-T-A27	A27	A42	R-L-A42
A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16	L-T-A28	A28	A43	R-L-A43
A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13	L-T-A29	A29	A44	R-L-A44
6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	L-T-A30	A30	A45	R-L-A45
A20	5*T-A25+A26-A13+A18+A8-5*S+A7-A14+A10+A20-A16-A15-A17-L	(9*L-17*T)/2-A23-A22-A21-A24+A25-A26+A13-A18-A8+5*S-A7+A14-A10-2*A20+A16+A15+A17	A21	A22	A23	A24	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A20	2*L-6*T+A25-A26+A13-A18-A8+5*S-A7+A14-A10-A20+A16+A15+A17	(15*T-7*L)/2+A23+A22+A21+A24-A25+A26-A13+A18+A8-5*S+A7-A14+A10+2*A20-A16-A15-A17	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	(9/2)*R-A44-A45-A46-A41-A42-A43-A39-A40-(9/2)*L	(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A44+A45+A46+A41+A42+A43+A39+A40
5*T+R-A15-A17+A32-A14+A10+2*A20+A7-A13+A18+A23+A22+A24-A11+2*A21-2*A16+2*A8-A29-A30-2*A25-2*A27-A28-7*S-A39+A40-L	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	(7/2)*R+A15+A17-2*A32+A14-A10-2*A20-A7+A13-A18-A23-A22-A24+A11-2*A21+2*A16-2*A8+A29+A30+2*A25+2*A27+A28-A34-A33+7*S-A37-A38+A39-A40-A35-A36-(7/2)*L-5*T	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
A15+A17-A32+A14-A10-2*A20-A7+A13-A18-A23-A22-A24+A11-2*A21+2*A16-2*A8+A29+A30+2*A25+2*A27+A28+7*S+A39-A40-5*T	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	5*T-(5/2)*R-A15-A17+2*A32-A14+A10+2*A20+A7-A13+A18+A23+A22+A24-A11+2*A21-2*A16+2*A8-A29-A30-2*A25-2*A27-A28+A34+A33-7*S+A37+A38-A39+A40+A35+A36+(5/2)*L	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. It contains magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.14. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										210
	26	65	19	-82	20	21	27	40	34	48	-8	210
	23	10	11	5	12	13	22	39	35	49	-9	210
	81	22	14	1	15	-1	-36	34	40	50	-10	210
	24	6	3	16	24	2	21	38	36	51	-11	210
	25	18	12	7	-6	20	20	37	37	52	-12	210
	22	-5	11	22	6	17	23	36	38	53	-13	210
	-105	-20	26	127	25	24	19	35	39	54	-14	210
	29	44	60	30	31	32	33	37	-126	55	-15	210
	45	30	14	44	43	42	41	-126	37	-232	272	210
	96	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	-224	20	10	210
	-56	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	264	10	20	210
	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

The magic square given in Example 2.14 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									170
	26	65	19	-82	20	21	27	40	34	170	
	23	10	11	5	12	13	22	39	35	170	
	81	22	14	1	15	-1	-36	34	40	170	
	24	6	3	16	24	2	21	38	36	170	
	25	18	12	7	-6	20	20	37	37	170	
	22	-5	11	22	6	17	23	36	38	170	
	-105	-20	26	127	25	24	19	35	39	170	
	29	44	60	30	31	32	33	37	-126	170	
	45	30	14	44	43	42	41	-126	37	170	
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	

7	semi							-27
	26	65	19	-82	20	21	27	96
	23	10	11	5	12	13	22	96
	81	22	14	1	15	-1	-36	96
	24	6	3	16	24	2	21	96
	25	18	12	7	-6	20	20	96
	22	-5	11	22	6	17	23	96
	-105	-20	26	127	25	24	19	96
	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96

5	pan	51	51	51	51	51	
	51	10	11	5	12	13	51
	51	22	14	1	15	-1	51
	51	6	3	16	24	2	51
	51	18	12	7	-6	20	51
		-5	11	22	6	17	51
		51	51	51	51	51	51

Result 2.15. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

A15	$(7/2)*T-(9/2)*S-A8+A5-2*M-A11$	A8	$(9/2)*S-A15-A16-A10-A9-A5+2*M-(5/2)*T+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A23	L-T-A23	A37	R-L-A37
$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A15+A16-A14+2*A8-A5+2*M-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A11-2*A8+A5-2*M+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A24	L-T-A24	A38	R-L-A38
$A5-(7/2)*S-2*M+(5/2)*T-2*A8$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	$(5/2)*S-(3/2)*T+2*A8-A5+2*M$	A25	L-T-A25	A39	R-L-A39
A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A26	L-T-A26	A40	R-L-A40
A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$	A41	R-L-A41
A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	T-S-A11	A27	L-T-A27	A42	R-L-A42
$6*S-A16-4*T$	$A11+A8-A5+(7/2)*S+2*M-(5/2)*T$	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+(7/2)*T-(11/2)*S+A5-2*M-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28	A43	R-L-A43
A18	$(5*T-3*M)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*M)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*M-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$5*T-(7*L+3*M)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$	$(9/2)*R-(9/2)*L-A39-A38-A37-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A39+A38+A37+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40$
$R-A37+A38-A25+A26-(3/2)*S-A14-(1/2)*M-A9+A20-A19+A30$	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	$(7/2)*R-A35-A34-A26+A25-2*A30-A20+A14-A33+A19-A32-A31+A9-A38+A37-A36+(3/2)*S+(1/2)*M-(9/2)*L$	$(R-L)/2$	$5*L-4*R$
$A37-A38+A25-A26+(3/2)*S+A14+(1/2)*M+A9-A20+A19-A30-L$	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$(7/2)*L-(5/2)*R+A35+A34+A26-A25+2*A30+A20-A14+A33-A19+A32+A31-A9+A38-A37+A36-(3/2)*S-(1/2)*M$	$5*L-4*R$	$(R-L)/2$

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. Again it contains a **cornered** magic square of order 5 having magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.15. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										240
	24	-137	126	-49	18	19	25	32	-20	46	156	240
	223	12	-3	3	-23	27	-213	33	-21	47	155	240
	-253	-5	4	13	14	-10	263	34	-22	48	154	240
	22	5	11	-4	15	-11	-12	35	-23	49	153	240
	23	115	90	-199	2	8	-13	-165	177	50	152	240
	20	-111	-86	203	8	2	-10	36	-24	51	151	240
	-33	147	-116	59	-8	-9	-14	37	-25	52	150	240
	150	-178	28	29	-48	30	31	6	-10	53	149	240
	-138	190	-16	-17	60	-18	-19	-10	6	513	-311	240
	372	200	40	41	42	43	44	45	82	101	-770	240
	-170	2	162	161	160	159	158	157	120	-770	101	240
	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

The magic square given in Example 2.4 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									38
	24	-137	126	-49	18	19	25	32	-20	38	
	223	12	-3	3	-23	27	-213	33	-21	38	
	-253	-5	4	13	14	-10	263	34	-22	38	
	22	5	11	-4	15	-11	-12	35	-23	38	
	23	115	90	-199	2	8	-13	-165	177	38	
	20	-111	-86	203	8	2	-10	36	-24	38	
	-33	147	-116	59	-8	-9	-14	37	-25	38	
	150	-178	28	29	-48	30	31	6	-10	38	
	-138	190	-16	-17	60	-18	-19	-10	6	38	
	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	

7	semi								8
	24	-137	126	-49	18	19	25	26	
	223	12	-3	3	-23	27	-213	26	
	-253	-5	4	13	14	-10	263	26	
	22	5	11	-4	15	-11	-12	26	
	23	115	90	-199	2	8	-13	26	
	20	-111	-86	203	8	2	-10	26	
	-33	147	-116	59	-8	-9	-14	26	
	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	

5	mgc						16
	12	-3	3	-23	27	16	
	-5	4	13	14	-10	16	
	5	11	-4	15	-11	16	
	115	90	-199	2	8	16	
	-111	-86	203	8	2	16	
	16	16	16	16	16	16	

3	mgc				12
	12	-3	3	12	
	-5	4	13	12	
	5	11	-4	12	
	12	12	12	12	

Result 2.16. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

A18	$T-S+A11+A15-A14$	A11	$S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	A19	$L-S-A21+A22-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+A27-A1$	$S-T+A21-A22+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-A27+A1$	A41	R-L-A41
$5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	S-M-A7	A8	A9	$5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18$	A27	L-T-A27	$A28-A29+A12-A24+S+A17+A23-A34+A33+A41-R+M+A6$	$2*R-L-A28+A29-A12+A24-S-A17-A23+A34-A33-A41-M-A6$
A15	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28	A42	R-L-A42
A16	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	S-M-A5	T-S-A16	A29	L-T-A29	A43	R-L-A43
A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17	$(5*L-7*T)/2+A21-A22+S+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-2*A27+A1-A28-A29-A30-A31$	$(5*T-3*L)/2-A21+A22-S-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+2*A27-A1+A28+A29+A30+A31$	$(11*R-9*L)/2-2*A41-A28+A29-A12+A24-S-A17-A23+A34-A33-M-A6-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47$	$(7*L-9*R)/2+2*A41+A28-A29+A12-A24+S+A17+A23-A34+A33+M+A6+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47$
A14	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14	A30	L-T-A30	A44	R-L-A44
$6*S-A19-4*T$	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	$A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A31	L-T-A31	A45	R-L-A45
A21	A22	A23	A24	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	A25	A26	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	A47	R-L-A47
A33	A34	A35	A36	$9*(R-L)/2-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A37	A38	A39	A40	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$7*(L-R)/2+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 7 and 5 at upper-left corner having magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.16. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										170
	27	46	20	-74	21	22	28	39	1	50	-10	170
	-37	15	-13	28	17	18	62	36	4	25	15	170
	24	87	14	3	4	-43	1	37	3	51	-11	170
	25	14	-3	7	17	30	0	38	2	52	-12	170
	26	13	10	11	0	31	-1	-89	129	-216	256	170
	23	-64	57	16	27	29	2	39	1	53	-13	170
	2	-21	5	99	4	3	-2	40	0	54	-14	170
	30	31	32	33	-55	34	35	20	-30	55	-15	170
	10	9	8	7	95	6	5	-30	20	56	-16	170
	42	43	44	45	-184	46	47	48	49	20	-30	170
	-2	-3	-4	-5	224	-6	-7	-8	-9	-30	20	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

The magic square given in Example 2.16 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									130
	27	46	20	-74	21	22	28	39	1	130	
	-37	15	-13	28	17	18	62	36	4	130	
	24	87	14	3	4	-43	1	37	3	130	
	25	14	-3	7	17	30	0	38	2	130	
	26	13	10	11	0	31	-1	-89	129	130	
	23	-64	57	16	27	29	2	39	1	130	
	2	-21	5	99	4	3	-2	40	0	130	
	30	31	32	33	-55	34	35	20	-30	130	
	10	9	8	7	95	6	5	-30	20	130	
	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	

7	semi								5
	27	46	20	-74	21	22	28	90	
	-37	15	-13	28	17	18	62	90	
	24	87	14	3	4	-43	1	90	
	25	14	-3	7	17	30	0	90	
	26	13	10	11	0	31	-1	90	
	23	-64	57	16	27	29	2	90	
	2	-21	5	99	4	3	-2	90	
	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	

5	semi						-25
	15	-13	28	17	18	65	
	87	14	3	4	-43	65	
	14	-3	7	17	30	65	
	13	10	11	0	31	65	
	-64	57	16	27	29	65	
	65	65	65	65	65	65	

3	mgc				21
	14	3	4	21	
	-3	7	17	21	
	10	11	0	21	
	21	21	21	21	

Result 2.17. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

A1	M-A1-A3	A3	A5	M-A5-A7	A7	A9	M-A9-A11	A11	A43	R-3*M-A43
M-A1-A2	A1+A2+A3+A4-M	M-A3-A4	M-A5-A6	A5+A6+A7+A8-M	M-A7-A8	M-A9-A10	$3*A16+4*A1+2*A2+2*A3+4*A4+3*A18+4*A31+2*A32+2*A33+4*A34-2*A25-A23-2*A24-A26-A10-A11-7*M$	$A11+A9+2*A10-3*A16-4*A1-2*A2-2*A3-4*A4+7*M-3*A18-4*A31-2*A32-2*A33-4*A34+2*A25+A23+2*A24+A26$	A44	R-3*M-A44
A2	M-A2-A4	A4	A6	M-A6-A8	A8	A10	$A10+2*A11+A9-3*A16-4*A1-2*A2-2*A3-4*A4+7*M-3*A18-4*A31-2*A32-2*A33-4*A34+2*A25+A23+2*A24+A26$	$3*A16+4*A1+2*A2+2*A3+4*A4+3*A18+4*A31+2*A32+2*A33+4*A34-2*A25-A23-2*A24-A26-2*A11-A9-2*A10-6*M$	A45	R-3*M-A45
A12	M-A12-A14	A14	A16	M-A16-A17	A17	A19	M-A19-A21	A21	A46	R-3*M-A46
M-A12-A13	A12+A13+A14+A15-M	M-A14-A15	$A16+2*A1+A2+A3+2*A4+A17+2*A18+2*A31+A32+A33+2*A34-5*M$	$5*M-A18-2*A31-A32-A33-2*A34-A16-2*A1-A2-A3-2*A4$	M-A17-A18	M-A19-A20	A19+A20+A21+A22-M	M-A21-A22	A47	R-3*M-A47
A13	M-A13-A15	A15	$6*M-2*A16-A17-2*A18-2*A31-A32-A33-2*A34-2*A1-A2-A3-2*A4$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A4+2*A16+6+A17+A18+2*A31+A32+A33+2*A34-5*M$	A18	A20	M-A20-A22	A22	A48	R-3*M-A48
A23	M-A23-A25	A25	A27	M-A27-A29	A29	A31	M-A31-A33	A33	A49	R-3*M-A49
M-A23-A24	A23+A24+A25+A26-M	M-A25-A26	M-A27-A28	A27+A28+A29+A30-M	M-A29-A30	M-A31-A32	A31+A32+A33+A34-M	M-A33-A34	A50	R-3*M-A50
A24	M-A24-A26	A26	A28	M-A28-A30	A30	A32	M-A32-A34	A34	$(9/2)*R-(9/2)*3*M-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50$	$(7/2)*3*M-(7/2)*R+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50$
$R+4*A34-2*A25-A23-A21-2*A24-2*A10-A29-A20-A28-2*A27+4*A4+2*A33-2*A11+4*A18-2*A19+3*A16+2*A32+4*A31-A9+A36+2*A3+4*A1+2*A2-8*M+A44-A43$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	$(7/2)*R-4*A34+2*A25+A23+A21+2*A24+2*A10+A29+A20+A28+2*A27-4*A4-2*A33+2*A11-4*A18+2*A19-3*A16-2*A32-4*A31+A9-A39-A38-A37-2*A36-2*A3-4*A1-2*A2-(11/2)*M-A44+A43-A42-A41-A40$	$(R-3*M)/2$	$5*3*M-4*R$
$2*A25+A23+A21+2*A24+2*A10+A29+A20+A28+2*A27-4*A4-2*A33+2*A11-4*A18+2*A19-3*A16-2*A32-4*A31+A9-A36-2*A3-4*A1-2*A2+5*M-A44+A43-4*A34$	R-3*M-A36	R-3*M-A37	R-3*M-A38	R-3*M-A39	R-3*M-A40	R-3*M-A41	R-3*M-A42	$4*A34-2*A25-A23-A21-2*A24-2*A10-A29-A20-A28-2*A27+4*A4+2*A33-2*A11+4*A18-2*A19+3*A16+2*A32+4*A31-A9+A39+A38+A37+2*A36+2*A3+4*A1+2*A2+(5/2)*M+A44-A43+A42+A41+A40-(5/2)*R$	$5*3*M-4*R$	$(R-3*M)/2$

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **block-wise** magic square of order 9 at the upper-left corner. It is composed of 9 equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are of equal width and length. The letters M L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 9 and 11 respectively. In this case $T = 3 \times M$. See below an example.

Example 2.17. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										170
	10	25	16	22	1	28	34	-23	40	136	-119	170
	28	7	16	4	55	-8	-20	859	-788	139	-122	170
	13	19	19	25	-5	31	37	-785	799	142	-125	170
	43	-41	49	55	-62	58	64	-83	70	145	-128	170
	-38	139	-50	694	-575	-68	-80	223	-92	148	-131	170
	46	-47	52	-698	688	61	67	-89	73	151	-134	170
	76	-107	82	88	-131	94	100	-155	106	154	-137	170
	-104	271	-116	-128	319	-140	-152	367	-164	157	-140	170
	79	-113	85	91	-137	97	103	-161	109	-1096	1113	170
	505	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	-1297	8.5	85	170
	-488	-98	-101	-104	-107	-110	-113	-116	1314	85	8.5	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

The magic square given in Example 2.17 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									153	semi	45	72	36	semi	9	36	108	semi	-1539	756	936		
	10	25	16	22	1	28	34	-23	40	153		10	25	16	51		22	1	28	51		34	-23	40	51
	28	7	16	4	55	-8	-20	859	-788	153		28	7	16	51		4	55	-8	51		-20	859	-788	51
	13	19	19	25	-5	31	37	-785	799	153		13	19	19	51		25	-5	31	51		37	-785	799	51
	43	-41	49	55	-62	58	64	-83	70	153		51	51	51	36		51	51	51	108		51	51	51	1692
	-38	139	-50	694	-575	-68	-80	223	-92	153		semi	-54	-27	234		semi	675	693	-1215		semi	-117	-90	360
	46	-47	52	-698	688	61	67	-89	73	153		43	-41	49	51		55	-62	58	51		64	-83	70	51
	76	-107	82	88	-131	94	100	-155	106	153		-38	139	-50	51		694	-575	-68	51		-80	223	-92	51
	-104	271	-116	-128	319	-140	-152	367	-164	153		46	-47	52	51		-698	688	61	51		67	-89	73	51
	79	-113	85	91	-137	97	103	-161	109	153		51	51	51	234		51	51	51	-459		51	51	51	360
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153		semi	-153	-126	432		semi	-189	-162	504		semi	-225	-198	576
												76	-107	82	51		88	-131	94	51		100	-155	106	51
												-104	271	-116	51		-128	319	-140	51		-152	367	-164	51
												79	-113	85	51		91	-137	97	51		103	-161	109	51
												51	51	51	432		51	51	51	504		51	51	51	576

Result 2.18. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

L-T-A31	$T-L-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	A40	R-L-A40
L-T-A24	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A24	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A25	A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A25	$9*(R-L)/2-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40$	$7*(L-R)/2+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40$
L-T-A26	$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A26	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A27	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	S/3	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A27	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A28	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	S-A1-A2	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	A28	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A29	$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A29	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A30	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A30	A46	R-L-A46
$8*T-7*L+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	A47	R-L-A47
$R+3*(S-T)/2-L-A40+A41+2*A7+A8-A1-A2-A18+2*A4+A5+A33+A25$	A33	$7*(R-L)/2+3*(T-S)/2-A39-A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-2*A33+A40-A41-2*A7-A8+A1+A2+A18-2*A4-A5-A25$	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	$(R-L)/2$	$5*L-4*R$
$3*(T-S)/2+A40-A41-2*A7-A8+A1+A2+A18-2*A4-A5-A33-A25$	R-L-A33	$5*(L-R)/2+3*(S-T)/2+A39+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+2*A33-A40+A41+2*A7+A8-A1-A2-A18+2*A4+A5+A25$	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	$5*L-4*R$	$(R-L)/2$

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper-left corner. It contains a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 in with magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×9 are of equal width and length. The letters M, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.18. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										170
	-2	119	28	29	30	31	32	33	-200	50	20	170
	5	-8	24	34	-6	-7	19	5	34	51	19	170
	4	23	22	-20	20	21	9	-14	35	-113	183	170
	3	44	-30	12	10	11	-14	28	36	52	18	170
	2	-11	25	10	11	12	17	-3	37	53	17	170
	1	-12	26	11	12	10	18	-4	38	54	16	170
	0	27	16	-8	14	15	-19	16	39	55	15	170
	-1	-2	-22	22	0	-1	31	33	40	56	14	170
	88	-80	11	10	9	8	7	6	41	57	13	170
	151	43	-158	44	45	46	47	48	49	35	-180	170
	-81	27	228	26	25	24	23	22	21	-180	35	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

The magic square given in Example 2.18 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									-51
	-2	119	28	29	30	31	32	33	-200	100	
	5	-8	24	34	-6	-7	19	5	34	100	
	4	23	22	-20	20	21	9	-14	35	100	
	3	44	-30	12	10	11	-14	28	36	100	
	2	-11	25	10	11	12	17	-3	37	100	
	1	-12	26	11	12	10	18	-4	38	100	
	0	27	16	-8	14	15	-19	16	39	100	
	-1	-2	-22	22	0	-1	31	33	40	100	
	88	-80	11	10	9	8	7	6	41	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	

7	mgc								61
	-8	24	34	-6	-7	19	5	61	
	23	22	-20	20	21	9	-14	61	
	44	-30	12	10	11	-14	28	61	
	-11	25	10	11	12	17	-3	61	
	-12	26	11	12	10	18	-4	61	
	27	16	-8	14	15	-19	16	61	
	-2	-22	22	0	-1	31	33	61	
	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	

3	mgc				21
	14	3	4	21	
	-3	7	17	21	
	10	11	0	21	
	21	21	21	21	

Result 2.19. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

L-T-A49	T-A41-A40-A39-A38-A37-A36-L+2*A49+A48+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	L-A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42	A58	R-L-A58
L-T-A42	T+A16+A30+A12-A24+A26-A20-A19-A23+A8-A22-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8+A22+A21-A16-A30-A12	A42	A59	R-L-A59
L-T-A43	A6	A7	A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-A27-A31-A2-A10-A15	A24+A28+A27+A25+A20+A19+A29+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A2+A1-A34-3*A16-A32-A30-A12-A11-A10	T+A34+3*A16+A15+A32+A31+A30+A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A28-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A9-A6-A22-A5-A4-A1-A21	A8	A9	A43	A60	R-L-A60
L-T-A44	A24-A26-A25+A20+A23-A8-A6+A22+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A16-A14-2*A30-A12	A18-A16+A14+A33+A30-A13-A12-A11-2*A10+A25+A19+A23+A8-A7+A6-A22+A5-A34	A10	A11	A12	T+A34-A18+2*A16-A33+A30+A12+A10-A24+A26-A20-A19-2*A23+A7-2*A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A13	A44	A61	R-L-A61
L-T-A45	A14	A34-A18-A17-2*A16-A15-A14-A30+A13-A12+2*A24-A26+A20+A19+A29+A23+A9-A8+A22+A21	A15	A16	A17	A18	T-A34+A16+A30-A13+A12-2*A24+A26-A20-A19-A29-A23-A9+A8-A22-A21	A45	A62	R-L-A62
L-T-A46	A19	A20	T-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24	A21	A22	A23	A24	A46	A63	R-L-A63
L-T-A47	A25	A26	A27	T+A34+2*A16+A30+A12+A10-A24-A28-A27-A25-A20-A19-A29-A23+A8+A7-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A28	A29	A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A34-2*A16-A30-A12-A10	A47	A64	R-L-A64
L-T-A48	A30	T+A17+3*A16+A15-A33-A9+2*A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A6-A5-A1-A21	A31	A32	2*A24+A25+2*A20+2*A19+A29+2*A23+A9+A6+A5+A1+A21-A34-A17-3*A16-A15-A32-A31-A30-2*A12-A11-2*A10	A33	A34	A48	A65	R-L-A65
8*T+A49+A48+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42-7*L	2*L-2*T+A41+A40+A39+A38+A37+A36-2*A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	A49	(9/2)*R-(9/2)*L-A58-A59-A60-A61-A62-A63-A64-A65	(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A58+A59+A60+A61+A62+A63+A64+A65
R+A8+A59+A34-A25-A23-A21+A7+A22-A24-A58+A10+A30-A29-A20-A28-A27-A4+A12+A13+A18-A19+2*A16-A5+A31+A51-A36-A3-A1-A2+A43-L	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	(7/2)*R-A8-A59-A34+A25+A23+A21-A7-A54-A22-A57+A24+A58-A10-A30+A29-A53+A20+A28+A27+A4-A12-A13-A18+A19-2*A16+A5-A31-2*A51-A52-A55-A56+A36+A3+A1+A2-A43-(7/2)*L	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
A25+A23+A21-A7-A22+A24+A58-A10-A30+A29+A20+A28+A27+A4-A12-A13-A18+A19-2*A16+A5-A31-A51+A36+A3+A1+A2-A43-A8-A59-A34	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	A8+A59+A34-A25-A23-A21+A7+A54+A22+A57-A24-A58+A10+A30-A29+A53-A20-A28-A27-A4+A12+A13+A18-A19+2*A16-A5+A31+2*A51+A52+A55+A56-A36-A3-A1-A2+A43+(5/2)*L-(5/2)*R	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper-left corner with magic square of order 7 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×9 are of equal width and length. The letters T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.19. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										235
	-104	517	115	118	121	124	127	130	-973	181	-121	235
	-83	-73	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	184	-124	235
	-86	25	28	139	52	-184	31	34	136	187	-127	235
	-89	-119	145	37	40	43	-67	46	139	190	-130	235
	-92	49	205	52	55	58	61	-355	142	193	-133	235
	-95	64	67	-304	70	73	76	79	145	196	-136	235
	-98	82	85	88	-211	91	-104	94	148	199	-139	235
	-101	97	-415	100	103	25	106	109	151	202	-142	235
	923	-467	-65	-68	-71	-74	-77	-80	154	-1262	1322	235
	188	160	163	166	169	172	175	178	-1101	30	-65	235
	-128	-100	-103	-106	-109	-112	-115	-118	1161	-65	30	235
	235	235	235	235	235	235	235	235	235	235	235	235

The magic square given in Example 2.19 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									75
	-104	517	115	118	121	124	127	130	-973	175	
	-83	-73	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	175	
	-86	25	28	139	52	-184	31	34	136	175	
	-89	-119	145	37	40	43	-67	46	139	175	
	-92	49	205	52	55	58	61	-355	142	175	
	-95	64	67	-304	70	73	76	79	145	175	
	-98	82	85	88	-211	91	-104	94	148	175	
	-101	97	-415	100	103	25	106	109	151	175	
	923	-467	-65	-68	-71	-74	-77	-80	154	175	
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

7	mgc								125
	-73	10	13	16	19	22	118	125	
	25	28	139	52	-184	31	34	125	
	-119	145	37	40	43	-67	46	125	
	49	205	52	55	58	61	-355	125	
	64	67	-304	70	73	76	79	125	
	82	85	88	-211	91	-104	94	125	
	97	-415	100	103	25	106	109	125	
	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	

Result 2.20. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

L-T-A31	$T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18-L+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	$R-3*T-A18+A25+A12-A33+A16+2*A15+2*A10+2*A11+2*A14+2*S-A7+A34-L+A41$	$3*T+A18-A25-A12+A33-A16-2*A15-2*A10-2*A11-2*A14-2*S+A7-A34-A41$
L-T-A24	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	A24	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A25	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	A25	$3*T+7*R/2+A18-A25-A43-A46-A47-A44-A12+A33-A45-A42-7*L/2-A16-2*A15-2*A10-2*A11-2*A14-2*S+A7-A34-2*A41$	$A25+A43+A46+A47+A44+A12-A33+A45+A42+5*L/2+A16+2*A15+2*A10+2*A11+2*A14+2*S-A7+A34+2*A41-3*T-5*R/2-A18$
L-T-A26	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	A26	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A27	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A27	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A28	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	A28	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A29	T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	$A7+A8+3*T/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13-3*S/2$	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A29	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A30	A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	$S/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13-T/2$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A30	A46	R-L-A46
$8*T+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-4*7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	A47	R-L-A47
A33	a34	$9*(R-L)/2-A40-A39-A37-A34-A38-A36-A35-A33$	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
R-L-A33	R-L-A34	$7*(L-R)/2+A40+A39+A37+A34+A38+A36+A35+A33$	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper-left corner. It contains a **cornered** magic squares of orders 7 and with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.20. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										250
	-21	158	38	39	40	41	42	43	-190	150	-90	250
	-14	21	22	10	23	24	33	27	44	61	-1	250
	-15	33	25	12	26	4	34	26	45	-328	388	250
	-16	17	8	27	35	13	12	48	46	62	-2	250
	-17	29	23	18	-1	31	35	25	47	63	-3	250
	-18	0	22	33	17	28	36	24	48	64	-4	250
	-19	36	30	21	31	32	30	-20	49	65	-5	250
	-20	24	30	39	29	28	-20	30	50	66	-6	250
	330	-128	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	51	67	-7	250
	53	54	-182	55	56	57	58	59	60	30	-50	250
	7	6	242	5	4	3	2	1	0	-50	30	250
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

The magic square given in Example 2.20 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi									300
	-21	158	38	39	40	41	42	43	-190	190
	-14	21	22	10	23	24	33	27	44	190
	-15	33	25	12	26	4	34	26	45	190
	-16	17	8	27	35	13	12	48	46	190
	-17	29	23	18	-1	31	35	25	47	190
	-18	0	22	33	17	28	36	24	48	190
	-19	36	30	21	31	32	30	-20	49	190
	-20	24	30	39	29	28	-20	30	50	190
	330	-128	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	51	190
	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190

7	mgc								160
	21	22	10	23	24	33	27	160	
	33	25	12	26	4	34	26	160	
	17	8	27	35	13	12	48	160	
	29	23	18	-1	31	35	25	160	
	0	22	33	17	28	36	24	160	
	36	30	21	31	32	30	-20	160	
	24	30	39	29	28	-20	30	160	
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

5	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	21	22	10	23	24	100	
100	33	25	12	26	4	100	
100	17	8	27	35	13	100	
100	29	23	18	-1	31	100	
	0	22	33	17	28	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	

Result 2.21. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

L-T-A29	$T-A21-A20-A19-A18-A17-A16-L+2*A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22$	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21	L-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22	A38	R-L-A38
L-T-A22	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A22	A39	R-L-A39
L-T-A23	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A23	A40	R-L-A40
L-T-A24	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A24	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A25	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$	A25	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A26	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	A26	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A27	$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A27	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A28	$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A28	A45	R-L-A45
$8*T+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A21+A20+A19+A18+A17+A16-2*A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22$	L-T-A16	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	A29	$(9/2)*R-(9/2)*L-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45$
$R+5*T-2*A8+A23-A10-2*A4-2*A12-2*A13-A14-A16-2*A5+A31-2*A9+A39-A38-5*S+A1+A2-L$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	$(7/2)*R-5*T+2*A8-A35-A34-A23+A10+2*A4+2*A12+2*A13+A14-A33+A16-A32+2*A5-2*A31+2*A9-A39+A38-A37-A36+5*S-A1-A2-(7/2)*L$	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
$2*A8-A23+A10+2*A4+2*A12+2*A13+A14+A16+2*A5-A31+2*A9-A39+A38+5*S-A1-A2-5*T$	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	$5*T-(5/2)*R-2*A8+A35+A34+A23-A10-2*A4-2*A12-2*A13-A14+A33-A16+A32-2*A5+2*A31-2*A9+A39-A38+A37+A36-5*S+A1+A2+(5/2)*L$	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper-left corner. It contains a **cornered** magic squares of orders 7 and 5 with magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×2 , 2×5 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.21. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										270
	19	98	28	29	30	31	32	33	-70	50	-10	270
	26	3	28	29	44	6	21	39	34	51	-11	270
	25	46	20	-6	15	35	22	38	35	52	-12	270
	24	11	12	37	16	34	23	37	36	53	-13	270
	23	12	14	49	25	10	60	0	37	54	-14	270
	22	38	36	1	10	25	24	36	38	55	-15	270
	21	29	18	19	64	20	30	-10	39	56	-16	270
	20	31	42	41	-4	40	-10	30	40	57	-17	270
	50	-38	32	31	30	29	28	27	41	-248	288	270
	148	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	-290	20	70	270
	-108	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	330	70	20	270
	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270

The magic square given in Example 2.21 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								150
	19	98	28	29	30	31	32	33	-70	230
	26	3	28	29	44	6	21	39	34	230
	25	46	20	-6	15	35	22	38	35	230
	24	11	12	37	16	34	23	37	36	230
	23	12	14	49	25	10	60	0	37	230
	22	38	36	1	10	25	24	36	38	230
	21	29	18	19	64	20	30	-10	39	230
	20	31	42	41	-4	40	-10	30	40	230
	50	-38	32	31	30	29	28	27	41	230
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230

7	mgc							170
	3	28	29	44	6	21	39	170
	46	20	-6	15	35	22	38	170
	11	12	37	16	34	23	37	170
	12	14	49	25	10	60	0	170
	38	36	1	10	25	24	36	170
	29	18	19	64	20	30	-10	170
	31	42	41	-4	40	-10	30	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

5	mgc						110
	3	28	29	44	6	110	
	46	20	-6	15	35	110	
	11	12	37	16	34	110	
	12	14	49	25	10	110	
	38	36	1	10	25	110	
	110	110	110	110	110	110	

3	mgc			60
	3	28	29	60
	46	20	-6	60
	11	12	37	60
	60	60	60	60

Result 2.22. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

L-T-A31	$T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18-L+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	A40	R-L-A40
L-T-A24	A15	$T-S+A8+A12-A11$	A8	$S-A15-A16-A10-A9-2*A8-A12+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A24	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A25	$5*T-6*S-A15+A16-A14-A12-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$5*S-4*T+A11+A12+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A25	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A26	A12	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	T-S-A12	A26	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A27	A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A27	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A28	A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	T-S-A14	A28	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A29	A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	T-S-A11	A29	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A30	$6*S-A16-4*T$	A11-A8-A12	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+2*A8+T-2*S+A12-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A30	A47	R-L-A47
$8*T+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	$(9/2)*R-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-(9/2)*L$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40$
$R+T-A8+A25+2*A4-A12+A33-A18+2*A5-(3/2)*S-A1-A2-(1/2)*M+A41-L-A40$	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	$(7/2)*R-T+A8-A35-A34-A25-2*A4+A12-2*A33+A18-2*A5-A39-A38-A37-A36+(3/2)*S+A1+A2+(1/2)*M-A41-(7/2)*L+A40$	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
$A8-A25-2*A4+A12-A33+A18-2*A5+(3/2)*S+A1+A2+(1/2)*M-A41+A40-T$	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	$(5/2)*L-(5/2)*R+T-A8+A35+A34+A25+2*A4-A12+2*A33-A18+2*A5+A39+A38+A37+A36-(3/2)*S-A1-A2-(1/2)*M+A41-A40$	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic squares of orders 9 and 7 at the upper-left corner. It contains a **cornered** magic squares of orders 5 with magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.22. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										331
	20	99	29	30	31	32	33	34	-29	51	1	331
	27	16	54	34	18	19	24	52	35	52	0	331
	26	23	-7	48	49	28	25	51	36	53	-1	331
	25	29	86	30	-26	22	88	-12	37	54	-2	331
	24	14	11	12	67	37	26	50	38	55	-3	331
	23	59	-3	17	33	35	27	49	39	56	-4	331
	22	63	21	61	22	23	38	-11	40	57	-5	331
	21	13	55	15	54	53	-11	38	41	58	-6	331
	91	-37	33	32	31	30	29	28	42	-202	254	331
	-27	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-68	26	71	331
	79	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	120	71	26	331
	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331

The magic square given in Example 2.22 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									279
	20	99	29	30	31	32	33	34	-29	279	
	27	16	54	34	18	19	24	52	35	279	
	26	23	-7	48	49	28	25	51	36	279	
	25	29	86	30	-26	22	88	-12	37	279	
	24	14	11	12	67	37	26	50	38	279	
	23	59	-3	17	33	35	27	49	39	279	
	22	63	21	61	22	23	38	-11	40	279	
	21	13	55	15	54	53	-11	38	41	279	
	91	-37	33	32	31	30	29	28	42	279	
	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	

7	mgc								217
	16	54	34	18	19	24	52	217	
	23	-7	48	49	28	25	51	217	
	29	86	30	-26	22	88	-12	217	
	14	11	12	67	37	26	50	217	
	59	-3	17	33	35	27	49	217	
	63	21	61	22	23	38	-11	217	
	13	55	15	54	53	-11	38	217	
	217	217	217	217	217	217	217	217	

5	semi						168
	16	54	34	18	19	141	
	23	-7	48	49	28	141	
	29	86	30	-26	22	141	
	14	11	12	67	37	141	
	59	-3	17	33	35	141	
	141	141	141	141	141	141	

3	mgc				90
	-7	48	49	90	
	86	30	-26	90	
	11	12	67	90	
	90	90	90	90	

Result 2.23. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

L-T-A32	$T-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-L+2*A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25$	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	L-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A25	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	A14	T-S-A14	A25	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A26	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-2*A7-A8+A2+A1-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+2*A7+A8-A2-A1-A9+A6$	A15	T-S-A15	A26	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A27	$2*A7+A8-A2-A1$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-2*A7-A8+A2+A1$	$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17-A16-A15-A14$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14+A15+A16+A17$	A27	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A28	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	A28	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A29	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	A29	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A30	$T-S-A7+A11-A8+A15-A14$	A11	$A7+A8+(3/2)*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14-(3/2)*S$	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A30	A47	R-L-A47
L-T-A31	$A7-A11+A8-A15+A14$	T-S-A11	$(1/2)*S+A13+A12+2*A11-A7-A8+A15-A14-(1/2)*T$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A31	A48	R-L-A48
$8*T+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19-2*A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	A32	$(9/2)*R-(9/2)*L-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*R+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48$
$R-3*T-A8+A34+A26-A7-A6+2*A12+A13+2*A11+A17-A19+2*A16+2*A15+3*S-M+A42-A41-L$	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$(7/2)*R+3*T+A8-A35-2*A34-A26+A7+A6-2*A12-A13-2*A11-A17+A19-2*A16-2*A15-A39-A38-A37-A36-3*S+M-A42+A41-(7/2)*L-A40$	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
$3*T+A8-A34-A26+A7+A6-2*A12-A13-2*A11-A17+A19-2*A16-2*A15-3*S+M-A42+A41$	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	$A35+2*A34+A26-A7-A6+2*A12+A13+2*A11+A17-A19+2*A16+2*A15+A39+A38+A37+A36+3*S-M+A42-A41+(5/2)*L+A40-(5/2)*R-3*T-A8$	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper-left corner. It contains a **cornered** magic squares of orders 7 with a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner with magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×9 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.23. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										230
9	108	28	29	30	31	32	33	-100	50	-20	230	
16	25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	34	51	-21	230	
15	-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	35	52	-22	230	
14	22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	36	53	-23	230	
13	23	11	12	67	16	14	7	37	54	-24	230	
12	24	22	14	9	15	60	6	38	55	-25	230	
11	21	8	16	21	60	15	9	39	56	-26	230	
10	94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	40	57	-27	230	
100	-58	22	21	20	19	18	17	41	-293	323	230	
1	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	-188	15	80	230	
29	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	218	80	15	230	
230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	

The magic square given in Example 2.23 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									200
-3	124	30	31	32	33	34	35	-146	170		
4	27	51	20	-39	21	22	28	36	170		
3	24	11	12	50	13	14	6	37	170		
2	-47	23	15	2	16	44	77	38	170		
1	25	7	48	17	25	3	5	39	170		
0	26	19	13	8	39	21	4	40	170		
-1	23	40	12	23	7	18	7	41	170		
-2	52	-21	10	69	9	8	3	42	170		
166	-84	10	9	8	7	6	5	43	170		
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		

7	semi								180
27	51	20	-39	21	22	28	130		
24	11	12	50	13	14	6	130		
-47	23	15	2	16	44	77	130		
25	7	48	17	25	3	5	130		
26	19	13	8	39	21	4	130		
23	40	12	23	7	18	7	130		
52	-21	10	69	9	8	3	130		
130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130		

5	pan	100	100	100	100	100
100	11	12	50	13	14	100
100	23	15	2	16	44	100
100	7	48	17	25	3	100
100	19	13	8	39	21	100
	40	12	23	7	18	100
	100	100	100	100	100	100

Result 2.24. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

L-T-A33	$T-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-L+2*A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26$	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	L-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26	$A43-4*A19+R-A35+A13+A36-A18-A8+A27+5*A9-A7+A14-A10+A16+A15+A17-A20-L$	$4*A19+A35-A13-A36+A18+A8-A27-5*A9+A7-A14+A10-A16-A15-A17+A20-A43$
L-T-A26	A17	$T-S+A10+A14-A13$	A10	$S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	A18	A26	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A27	A14	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	T-S-A14	A27	$4*A19+7*(R-L)/2-A44+A35-A47-A46-A13-A36-A45+A18-A48-A49+A8-A27-5*A9+A7-A14+A10-A16-A15-A17+A20-2*A43$	$2*A43-4*A19-5*(R-L)/2+A44-A35+A47+A46+A13+A36+A45-A18+A48+A49-A8+A27+5*A9-A7+A14-A10+A16+A15+A17-A20$
L-T-A28	$5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13$	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	$5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17$	A28	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A29	A15	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8$	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	T-S-A15	A29	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A30	A16	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	T-S-A16	A30	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A31	A13	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	T-S-A13	A31	A47	R-L-A47
L-T-A32	$6*S-A18-4*T$	$A13-A10-A14$	T-S-A10	$A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	A32	A48	R-L-A48
$8*T+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20-2*A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26$	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	A33	A49	R-L-A49
A35	A36	$9*(R-L)/2-A42-A41-A39-A36-A40-A38-A37-A35$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	$(R-L)/2$	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$7*(L-R)/2+A42+A41+A39+A36+A40+A38+A37+A35$	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	$5*L-4*R$	$(R-L)/2$

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic squares of orders 9 and 7 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are of equal width and length. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.24. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										220
	-3	124	30	31	32	33	34	35	-146	133	-83	220
	4	27	51	20	-39	21	22	28	36	53	-3	220
	3	24	11	12	50	13	14	6	37	-300	350	220
	2	-47	23	15	2	16	44	77	38	54	-4	220
	1	25	7	48	17	25	3	5	39	55	-5	220
	0	26	19	13	8	39	21	4	40	56	-6	220
	-1	23	40	12	23	7	18	7	41	57	-7	220
	-2	52	-21	10	69	9	8	3	42	58	-8	220
	166	-84	10	9	8	7	6	5	43	59	-9	220
	45	46	-163	47	48	49	50	51	52	25	-30	220
	5	4	213	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-30	25	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The magic square given in Example 2.24 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								240
	9	108	28	29	30	31	32	33	-100	200
	16	25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	34	200
	15	-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	35	200
	14	22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	36	200
	13	23	11	12	67	16	14	7	37	200
	12	24	22	14	9	15	60	6	38	200
	11	21	8	16	21	60	15	9	39	200
	10	94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	40	200
	100	-58	22	21	20	19	18	17	41	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

7	semi								240
	25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	150	
	-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	150	
	22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	150	
	23	11	12	67	16	14	7	150	
	24	22	14	9	15	60	6	150	
	21	8	16	21	60	15	9	150	
	94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	150	
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	

5	mgc						120
	-7	48	49	14	16	120	
	86	30	-26	15	15	120	
	11	12	67	16	14	120	
	22	14	9	15	60	120	
	8	16	21	60	15	120	
	120	120	120	120	120	120	

3	mgc				90
	-7	48	49	90	
	86	30	-26	90	
	11	12	67	90	
	90	90	90	90	

Result 2.25. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

L-T-A28	$T-L-A34-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29+2*A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	L-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21	$A22-S-L-A15-A29+A37-A36-A11+A7-A1+A44+T-A2+R-A5$	$S-T+A15-A22+A29-A37+A36+A11-A7+A1-A44+A2+A5$
L-T-A21	A18	$T-S+A11+A15-A14$	A11	$S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	A19	A21	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A22	$5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	$S-M-A7$	A8	A9	$5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18$	A22	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A23	A15	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	T-S-A15	A23	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A24	A16	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-A5$	T-S-A16	A24	$7*(R-L)/2+S-T+A15-A22+A29-A37+A36+A11-A7+A1-2*A44+A2+A5-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50$	$5*(L-R)/2-S+T-A15+A22-A29+A37-A36-A11+A7-A1+2*A44-A2-A5+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50$
L-T-A25	A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	$S-M-A4$	T-S-A17	A25	A47	R-L-A47
L-T-A26	A14	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	$S-M-A8$	$S-M-A6$	T-S-A14	A26	A48	R-L-A48
L-T-A27	$6*S-A19-4*T$	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	$A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A27	A49	R-L-A49
$8*T-7*L+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21$	$2*L-2*T+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29-2*A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21$	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	A28	A50	R-L-A50
A36	A37	A38	A39	$9*(R-L)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	A40	A41	A42	A43	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	$7*(L-R)/2+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43$	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

• **Details:**

It is a **cornered** magic square of orders 11 having a **single-digit bordered** magic squares of orders 9, 7 and 5 with a magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are of equal width and length. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below an example.

Example 2.25. Let's consider an example based on above result:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJT										151
	-7	34	39	40	41	42	43	44	-145	30	-10	151
	0	28	51	21	-74	22	23	29	31	54	-34	151
	-1	-27	16	-12	30	18	19	56	32	55	-35	151
	-2	25	91	15	4	5	-44	4	33	56	-36	151
	-3	26	15	-2	8	18	32	3	34	-339	359	151
	-4	27	14	11	12	1	33	2	35	57	-37	151
	-5	24	-65	59	17	29	31	5	36	58	-38	151
	-6	-3	-22	8	103	7	6	1	37	59	-39	151
	159	-3	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	38	60	-40	151
	46	47	48	49	-306	50	51	52	53	10	51	151
	-26	-27	-28	-29	326	-30	-31	-32	-33	51	10	151
	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151

The magic square given in Example 2.25 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										18
	-7	34	39	40	41	42	43	44	-145			131
	0	28	51	21	-74	22	23	29	31			131
	-1	-27	16	-12	30	18	19	56	32			131
	-2	25	91	15	4	5	-44	4	33			131
	-3	26	15	-2	8	18	32	3	34			131
	-4	27	14	11	12	1	33	2	35			131
	-5	24	-65	59	17	29	31	5	36			131
	-6	-3	-22	8	103	7	6	1	37			131
	159	-3	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	38			131
	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131			131

7	semi									4
	28	51	21	-74	22	23	29		100	
	-27	16	-12	30	18	19	56		100	
	25	91	15	4	5	-44	4		100	
	26	15	-2	8	18	32	3		100	
	27	14	11	12	1	33	2		100	
	24	-65	59	17	29	31	5		100	
	-3	-22	8	103	7	6	1		100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		100	

5	semi						-22
	16	-12	30	18	19	71	
	91	15	4	5	-44	71	
	15	-2	8	18	32	71	
	14	11	12	1	33	71	
	-65	59	17	29	31	71	
	71	71	71	71	71	71	

3	mgc	45	3	24	
	15	15	4	5	24
	33	-2	8	18	24
		11	12	1	24
		24	24	24	24

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>

- (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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